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Evaluation of mechanical properties for CFRTP using *in situ*-polymerizing thermoplastic urethane resin

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Background

◆ Carbon Fiber Reinforced ThermoPlastics (CFRTP)

CFRTP has been attracting attention.

Melt viscosity of the thermoplastic resin is too high.

In situ-polymerizing thermoplastic resins

- Just monomer mixture with low viscosity.
- Rapidly polymerize after impregnation.

New Development

In situ-polymerizing thermoplastic urethane resin.

Background

Laminate fibers and impregnate resin

Push out excess resin

Heat and press

Low viscosity before curing.

PU-CFRTP can be molded by the same method as the ordinary CFRP.

Experiments

Our objective

Evaluate the mechanical properties for CFRTP using *in situ*-polymerizing urethane resin.

Constitute materials

Type of test specimen	Type of resin	Type of fiber
PU-CFRTP	Thermoplastic urethane resin H-6FP17 (DKS)	Twill woven carbon fiber fabric W-3161 (TEIJIN)
EP-CFRTP	Thermoplastic epoxy resin XNR6850A (Nagase ChemteX corporation)	
AC-CFRTP	Thermoplastic acrylic resin Elium 190 (ARKEMA)	
CFRP	Thermosetting epoxy resin XNR6805 (Nagase ChemteX corporation)	

Experiments

- **Three-point bending tests.**
- **Dynamic viscoelastic measurement.**
- **Bending test at elevated temperatures.**
- **Creep test.**

✂ Fiber volume content of all specimens are about 60%.

Results of dynamic viscoelastic measurement

	T _g [°C]
PU-CFRTP	161.8
EP-CFRTP	101.0
AC-CFRTP	128.4
CFRP	117.3

- Urethane has a remarkably high T_g compared with other resins.

Results of bending test at elevated temperatures

- PU-CFRTP always exhibited the highest strength.
- Urethane resin allowed CFRTP to deform more than the others.

Results of creep test (At 80°C, 30% of bending strength)

- Creep strain of PU-CFRTP is the smallest.
- PU-CFRTP exhibited the lowest value of creep strain rate.

PU-CFRTP has good creep resistance.

Conclusion

In this study, the following conclusions were obtained.

- ◆ The newly developed urethane resin has excellent moldability.
 - The same molding method as thermosetting resin can be applied.

- ◆ CFRTP using it has excellent mechanical properties.
 - High heat resistance
 - Excellent creep resistance